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Companies producing computers, electronic and optical products and electrical equipment in OECD countries

They decreased on average by 19.56% between 2005 and 2022 for the OECD countries considered

The OECD calculates the number of companies producing computers, electronic and optical products and electrical equipment. The data refers to the period between 2005 and 2022.

Computer, electronic, optical and electrical equipment companies in OECD countries in 2022. Computer, electronic, optical and electrical equipment companies in OECD countries in 2022 show a diverse and complex landscape, with notable differences between nations. Germany leads the ranking with a total of 14,128 companies, highlighting the crucial role of the technology sector in the German economy. Italy and the Czech Republic follow with 12,943 and 12,751 companies respectively, indicating a strong presence of this sector also in these countries. Poland ranks fourth with 6,236 companies, showing significant growth compared to previous years and a consolidation of its position as an emerging technology hub in Eastern Europe. France and Spain, with 4,938 and 4,018 companies respectively, represent important centers of technological production in Western Europe, albeit with smaller numbers than the industry leaders. The Slovak Republic, with 4,002 companies, demonstrates a growing economy with a solid technological industrial base. Countries such as the Netherlands (3,038 companies) and Hungary (2,285 companies) highlight a robust presence of technology companies, contributing significantly to their respective national economies. Sweden and Switzerland, despite having fewer companies (1,940 and 1,865 respectively), maintain a strong reputation for innovation and the high quality of their technological products. Romania and Serbia, with 1,479 and 1,360 companies respectively, show signs of growth and potential expansion in the technology sector. Finland, with 1,276 companies, reflects its tradition of technological excellence, especially in the field of telecommunications. Austria and Greece, with a similar number of companies (1,273 and 1,233 respectively), indicate a significant contribution to the technology sector in Central and Southern Europe. Belgium and Denmark, with 1,108 and 1,059 companies respectively, demonstrate the importance of the technology sector in their highly developed economies. Israel, with 972 companies, continues to be a world leader in technological innovation, despite the relatively small number of companies compared to other European countries. Countries such as Croatia (936 companies), Bulgaria (887 companies) and Portugal (859 companies) show growing interest and development in the technology sector, suggesting potential for future growth. Slovenia and Norway, with 692 and 525 companies respectively, maintain significant influence in the technology sector, despite their relatively small size. The Baltic republics, such as Latvia, Lithuania and Estonia (301, 288 and 278 companies respectively), reflect their commitment to technological innovation and the digitalisation of their economies. South-eastern European countries such as North Macedonia (185 companies) and Bosnia and Herzegovina (179 companies) show a technology sector that is still developing, with large margins for future growth. Costa Rica, with 147 companies, represents a significant presence in Central America's technology sector. Finally, smaller

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countries such as Cyprus (73 companies), Malta (43 companies) and Luxembourg (20 companies) reflect the challenges and opportunities of having a small number of technology companies in smaller economies. In summary, the sector of computer, electronic, optical and electrical equipment manufacturing companies in OECD countries is characterized by significant variability in terms of the number of active companies. This variability reflects the different economic, industrial and technological innovation dynamics present in each country. The data suggests that while some countries are already established leaders in the sector, others are emerging as new centers of technology growth, contributing substantially to the global technology landscape. The analysis of this data is essential to understand current and future trends in the technology sector in OECD countries and to identify opportunities for growth and development in this strategic field.

Companies producing computers, electronic and optical products and electrical equipment in OECD countries between 2005 and 2022. The comparison between 2005 and 2022 data relating to companies producing computers, electronic and optical products and electrical equipment in OECD countries reveals significant trends that reflect the economic and industrial transformations of these countries. Austria shows a slight growth in the number of companies, going from 1,210 to 1,273, with an absolute change of 63 companies and a percentage increase of 5.21%. This suggests stability in the Austrian tech sector, albeit with moderate growth. Costa Rica highlights notable growth, with an increase from 78 to 147 businesses, marking an absolute change of 69 businesses and a percentage increase of 88.46%. This sharp increase could be attributed to policies friendly to the technology industry and significant investments in innovation and technology production. The Czech Republic, on the other hand, shows a significant contraction, with a decrease from 19,102 to 12,751 companies, a negative absolute change of 6,351 companies and a percentage decrease of 33.25%. This decline could be the result of several dynamics, including the relocation of production, structural changes in the market or increased international competitiveness. Estonia recorded substantial growth, going from 179 to 278 companies, with an absolute change of 99 companies and a percentage increase of 55.31%. This suggests strong growth in the Estonian technology sector, likely supported by an environment conducive to innovation and technology adoption. Hungary shows a significant reduction in the number of companies, going from 3,925 to 2,285, with a negative absolute change of 1,640 companies and a percentage decrease of 41.78%. This decline may reflect economic difficulties or a reduction in the competitiveness of the Hungarian technology sector. Latvia shows an impressive increase, with the number of companies increasing from 132 to 301, marking an absolute change of 169 companies and a percentage increase of 128.03%. This growth could be indicative of accelerated technology adoption and government policies conducive to the development of the technology sector. Lithuania shows a more moderate growth, going from 258 to 288 companies, with an absolute change of 30 companies and a percentage increase of 11.63%. This suggests stable and continuous growth of the Lithuanian technology sector. Poland recorded significant growth, with an increase from 4,449 to 6,236 companies, marking an absolute change of 1,787 companies and a percentage increase of 40.17%. This reflects a strong expansion of the Polish technology sector, potentially supported by foreign investment and technological development policies. Portugal, on the other hand, shows a decrease in the number of companies, going from 1,324 to 859, with a negative absolute variation of 465 companies and a percentage decrease of 35.12%. This decline could be the result of economic difficulties, reduced domestic demand or reduced competitiveness in the technology sector. Slovenia recorded a reduction, going from 793 to 692 companies, with a negative absolute variation of 101 companies and a percentage decrease of 12.74%. This decline could reflect a restructuring of the sector or increased international competitiveness which has negatively impacted local businesses. Bulgaria shows marginal growth, going from 883 to 887 companies, with an absolute change of 4 companies and a percentage increase of 0.45%. This suggests a stability of the

Bulgarian technology sector, without significant expansions or contractions. Finally, Romania shows a reduction, going from 1,826 to 1,479 companies, with a negative absolute variation of 347 companies and a percentage decrease of 19.00%. This decline could be attributed to various factors, including the migration of businesses to more competitive markets or domestic economic difficulties.

Conclusions. The value of companies producing computers, electronic and optical products and electrical equipment in the OECD countries considered decreased on average by 19.56% between 2005 and 2022. There are countries in which the number of such companies has grown between 2005 and 2022 or Latvia with +128.03%, Costa Rica with +88.46%, Estonia with +55.31%. Among the countries that have seen the number of such companies reduce are the Czech Republic with -33.25%, Portugal with -35.12%, and Hungary with -41.78%.

Declarations

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